

**EXAMINING TECHNOLOGICAL, PEDAGOGICAL AND CONTENT KNOWLEDGE
(TPACK) OF SMNHS MATHEMATICS TEACHERS**

**A Research
Presented to the
Faculty of Graduate School
St. Paul University Philippines
Tuguegarao City, Cagayan**

**In partial fulfilment
Of the requirements for the course
Research Seminar in Mathematics Education**

**by
KRISTOFFER PAULO L. RAMIREZ
Ph.D in Mathematics Education
December 2019**

CHAPTER I THE PROBLEM AND REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Background of the Study

To be able to translate and contextualized information to improve student's understanding and motivation for learning, an effective teacher of the 21st century classroom requires a strong specialized knowledge across different cases and structures. This often include, not just on the content of the subject to be taught and the pedagogies that are to be used to effectively deliver the content, but also on the use of technologies which has significant effect on both the content and the pedagogy of what they are attempting to teach.

In this sense, effective teaching depends on flexible access to rich, well-organized and integrated knowledge from different domains (Glaser, 1984; Putnam & Borko, 2000; Shulman, 1986, 1987) including knowledge of student thinking and learning, knowledge of subject matter, and increasingly, knowledge of technology. By acknowledging the interconnection of these, one would be able to become an effective facilitator of 21st century learners.

As such there is a need to study the extent of knowledge of teachers on these three key domains which happened to be

described by the Technological, Pedagogical and Content Knowledge (TPACK) educational framework of Koehler and Mishra (2005).

TPACK is an educational framework build on Lee Shulman (1986) notion through his PCK (Pedagogical - Content - Knowledge) concept in his landmark paper, *Those Who Understand: Knowledge Growth in Teaching*, raising an issue on the need for a more coherent theoretical framework with regard to what teachers should know and be able to do. As argued by the main proponents, Koehler and Mishra (2005), there is a sufficient need to extend Shulman's model by incorporating the intersections of technological knowledge (TK) with both content knowledge (CK) and pedagogical knowledge (PK), producing three more intersections (TPK, TCK, and TPCK) since modern digital technologies which includes information and communication technology, have changed the nature of the classroom teaching and learning process.

By using Shulman's (1986) PCK framework and combining the relationships between content knowledge (subject matter that is to be taught), technological knowledge (computers and related technologies), and pedagogical knowledge

(practices, processes, strategies, procedures, and methods of teaching and learning), TPACK would allow a deeper understanding on teachers knowledge on these three important domains.

Hence this study.

Review of Literature

The TPACK Framework

*Note: The following text were directly lifted from the study of Matthew J. Koehler and Punya Mishra (2009), the main proponents, on their study **What is Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge?**.*

The TPACK framework builds on Shulman's (1987, 1986) descriptions of PCK to describe how teachers' understanding of educational technologies and PCK interact with one another to produce effective teaching with technology. Other authors have discussed similar ideas, though often using different labeling schemes. The conception of TPACK described here has developed over time and through a series of publications, with the most complete descriptions of the framework found in Mishra and Koehler (2006) and Koehler and Mishra (2008).

In this model (see Figure 1), there are three main components of teachers' knowledge: content, pedagogy, and

technology. Equally important to the model are the interactions between and among these bodies of knowledge, represented as PCK, TCK (technological content knowledge), TPK (technological pedagogical knowledge), and TPACK.

Figure 1. *The TPACK framework and its knowledge components.*

Content Knowledge

Content knowledge (CK) is teachers' knowledge about the subject matter to be learned or taught. The content to be covered in middle school science or history is different from the content to be covered in an undergraduate course on art appreciation or a graduate seminar on astrophysics. Knowledge of content is of critical importance for teachers. As Shulman (1986) noted, this knowledge would include

knowledge of concepts, theories, ideas, organizational frameworks, knowledge of evidence and proof, as well as established practices and approaches toward developing such knowledge. Knowledge and the nature of inquiry differ greatly between fields, and teachers should understand the deeper knowledge fundamentals of the disciplines in which they teach. In the case of science, for example, this would include knowledge of scientific facts and theories, the scientific method, and evidence-based reasoning. In the case of art appreciation, such knowledge would include knowledge of art history, famous paintings, sculptures, artists and their historical contexts, as well as knowledge of aesthetic and psychological theories for evaluating art.

The cost of not having a comprehensive base of content knowledge can be prohibitive; for example, students can receive incorrect information and develop misconceptions about the content area (National Research Council, 2000; Pfundt, & Duit, 2000). Yet content knowledge, in and of itself, is an ill-structured domain, and as the culture wars (Zimmerman, 2002), the Great Books controversies (Bloom, 1987; Casement, 1997; Levine, 1996), and court battles over the teaching of evolution (Pennock, 2001) demonstrate,

issues relating to curriculum content can be areas of significant contention and disagreement.

Pedagogical Knowledge

Pedagogical knowledge (PK) is teachers' deep knowledge about the processes and practices or methods of teaching and learning. They encompass, among other things, overall educational purposes, values, and aims. This generic form of knowledge applies to understanding how students learn, general classroom management skills, lesson planning, and student assessment. It includes knowledge about techniques or methods used in the classroom; the nature of the target audience; and strategies for evaluating student understanding. A teacher with deep pedagogical knowledge understands how students construct knowledge and acquire skills and how they develop habits of mind and positive dispositions toward learning. As such, pedagogical knowledge requires an understanding of cognitive, social, and developmental theories of learning and how they apply to students in the classroom.

Pedagogical Content Knowledge

PCK is consistent with and similar to Shulman's idea of knowledge of pedagogy that is applicable to the teaching

of specific content. Central to Shulman's conceptualization of PCK is the notion of the transformation of the subject matter for teaching. Specifically, according to Shulman (1986), this transformation occurs as the teacher interprets the subject matter, finds multiple ways to represent it, and adapts and tailors the instructional materials to alternative conceptions and students' prior knowledge.

PCK covers the core business of teaching, learning, curriculum, assessment and reporting, such as the conditions that promote learning and the links among curriculum, assessment, and pedagogy. An awareness of common misconceptions and ways of looking at them, the importance of forging connections among different content-based ideas, students' prior knowledge, alternative teaching strategies, and the flexibility that comes from exploring alternative ways of looking at the same idea or problem are all essential for effective teaching.

Technology Knowledge

Technology knowledge (TK) is always in a state of flux—more so than the other two core knowledge domains in the TPACK framework (pedagogy and content). Thus, defining it is notoriously difficult. Any definition of technology

knowledge is in danger of becoming outdated by the time this text has been published. That said, certain ways of thinking about and working with technology can apply to all technology tools and resources.

The definition of TK used in the TPACK framework is close to that of Fluency of Information Technology (FITness), as proposed by the Committee of Information Technology Literacy of the National Research Council (NRC, 1999). They argue that FITness goes beyond traditional notions of computer literacy to require that persons understand information technology broadly enough to apply it productively at work and in their everyday lives, to recognize when information technology can assist or impede the achievement of a goal, and to continually adapt to changes in information technology. FITness, therefore, requires a deeper, more essential understanding and mastery of information technology for information processing, communication, and problem solving than does the traditional definition of computer literacy.

Acquiring TK in this manner enables a person to accomplish a variety of different tasks using information technology and to develop different ways of accomplishing a

given task. This conceptualization of TK does not posit an “end state,” but rather sees it developmentally, as evolving over a lifetime of generative, open-ended interaction with technology.

Technological Content Knowledge

Technology and content knowledge have a deep historical relationship. Progress in fields as diverse as medicine, history, archeology, and physics have coincided with the development of new technologies that afford the representation and manipulation of data in new and fruitful ways. Consider Roentgen’s discovery of X-rays or the technique of carbon-14 dating and the influence of these technologies in the fields of medicine and archeology. Consider also how the advent of the digital computer changed the nature of physics and mathematics and placed a greater emphasis on the role of simulation in understanding phenomena.

Technological changes have also offered new metaphors for understanding the world. Viewing the heart as a pump, or the brain as an information processing machine are just some of the ways in which technologies have provided new perspectives for understanding phenomena. These

representational and metaphorical connections are not superficial. They often have led to fundamental changes in the natures of the disciplines.

Understanding the impact of technology on the practices and knowledge of a given discipline is critical to developing appropriate technological tools for educational purposes. The choice of technologies affords and constrains the types of content ideas that can be taught. Likewise, certain content decisions can limit the types of technologies that can be used. Technology can constrain the types of possible representations, but also can afford the construction of newer and more varied representations. Furthermore, technological tools can provide a greater degree of flexibility in navigating across these representations.

TCK, then, is an understanding of the manner in which technology and content influence and constrain one another. Teachers need to master more than the subject matter they teach; they must also have a deep understanding of the manner in which the subject matter (or the kinds of representations that can be constructed) can be changed by the application of particular technologies. Teachers need to understand

which specific technologies are best suited for addressing subject-matter learning in their domains and how the content dictates or perhaps even changes the technology—or vice versa.

Technological Pedagogical Knowledge

TPK is an understanding of how teaching and learning can change when particular technologies are used in particular ways. This includes knowing the pedagogical affordances and constraints of a range of technological tools as they relate to disciplinarily and developmentally appropriate pedagogical designs and strategies. To build TPK, a deeper understanding of the constraints and affordances of technologies and the disciplinary contexts within which they function is needed.

For example, consider how whiteboards may be used in classrooms. Because a whiteboard is typically immobile, visible to many, and easily editable, its uses in classrooms are presupposed. Thus, the whiteboard is usually placed at the front of the classroom and is controlled by the teacher. This location imposes a particular physical order in the classroom by determining the placement of tables and chairs and framing the nature of student-teacher interaction, since

students often can use it only when called upon by the teacher.

However, it would be incorrect to say that there is only one way in which whiteboards can be used. One has only to compare the use of a whiteboard in a brainstorming meeting in an advertising agency setting to see a rather different use of this technology. In such a setting, the whiteboard is not under the purview of a single individual. It can be used by anybody in the group, and it becomes the focal point around which discussion and the negotiation/construction of meaning occurs. An understanding of the affordances of technology and how they can be leveraged differently according to changes in context and purposes is an important part of understanding TPK.

TPK becomes particularly important because most popular software programs are not designed for educational purposes. Software programs such as the Microsoft Office Suite (Word, PowerPoint, Excel, Entourage, and MSN Messenger) are usually designed for business environments. Web-based technologies such as blogs or podcasts are designed for purposes of entertainment, communication, and social networking. Teachers need to reject functional fixedness (Duncker, 1945)

and develop skills to look beyond most common uses for technologies, reconfiguring them for customized pedagogical purposes.

Thus, TPK requires a forward-looking, creative, and open-minded seeking of technology use, not for its own sake but for the sake of advancing student learning and understanding.

Technology, Pedagogy, and Content Knowledge

TPACK is an emergent form of knowledge that goes beyond all three “core” components (content, pedagogy, and technology). Technological pedagogical content knowledge is an understanding that emerges from interactions among content, pedagogy, and technology knowledge. Underlying truly meaningful and deeply skilled teaching with technology,

TPACK is different from knowledge of all three concepts individually. Instead, TPACK is the basis of effective teaching with technology, requiring an understanding of the representation of concepts using technologies; pedagogical techniques that use technologies in constructive ways to teach content; knowledge of what makes concepts difficult or easy to learn and how technology can help redress some

of the problems that students face; knowledge of students' prior knowledge and theories of epistemology; and knowledge of how technologies can be used to build on existing knowledge to develop new epistemologies or strengthen old ones.

By simultaneously integrating knowledge of technology, pedagogy and content, expert teachers bring TPACK into play any time they teach. Each situation presented to teachers is a unique combination of these three factors, and accordingly, there is no single technological solution that applies for every teacher, every course, or every view of teaching. Rather, solutions lie in the ability of a teacher to flexibly navigate the spaces defined by the three elements of content, pedagogy, and technology and the complex interactions among these elements in specific contexts. Ignoring the complexity inherent in each knowledge component or the complexities of the relationships among the components can lead to oversimplified solutions or failure. Thus, teachers need to develop fluency and cognitive flexibility not just in each of the key domains (T, P, and C), but also in the manner in which these domains and contextual parameters interrelate, so that they can

construct effective solutions. This is the kind of deep, flexible, pragmatic, and nuanced understanding of teaching with technology we involved in considering TPACK as a professional knowledge construct.

The act of seeing technology, pedagogy, and content as three interrelated knowledge bases is not straightforward.

As said before,

... separating the three components (content, pedagogy, and technology) ... is an analytic act and one that is difficult to tease out in practice. In actuality, these components exist in a state of dynamic equilibrium or, as the philosopher Kuhn (1977) said in a different context, in a state of "essential tension".... Viewing any of these components in isolation from the others represents a real disservice to good teaching. Teaching and learning with technology exist in a dynamic transactional relationship (Bruce, 1997; Dewey & Bentley, 1949; Rosenblatt, 1978) between the three components in our framework; a change in any one of the factors has to be "compensated" by changes in the other two. (Mishra & Koehler, 2006, p. 1029)

This compensation is most evident whenever using a new educational technology suddenly forces teachers to confront

basic educational issues and reconstruct the dynamic equilibrium among all three elements. This view inverts the conventional perspective that pedagogical goals and technologies are derived from content area curricula. Things are rarely that simple, particularly when newer technologies are employed. The introduction of the Internet, for example - particularly the rise of online learning - is an example of the arrival of a technology that forced educators to think about core pedagogical issues, such as how to represent content on the Web and how to connect students with subject matter and with one another (Peruski & Mishra, 2004).

Teaching with technology is a difficult thing to do well. The TPACK framework suggests that content, pedagogy, technology, and teaching/learning contexts have roles to play individually and together. Teaching successfully with technology requires continually creating, maintaining, and re-establishing a dynamic equilibrium among all components. It is worth noting that a range of factors influences how this equilibrium is reached.

Statement of the Problems

This research will focus on answering one basic research question: What is the extent of Technological Pedagogical and Content Knowledge (TPACK) of secondary mathematics teachers of Sta. Marcela National High School (SMNHS)?

Specifically, it aims to determine the extent to which the secondary mathematics teachers demonstrates the following indicators:

1. Technological knowledge (TK);
2. Pedagogical knowledge (PK);
3. Content knowledge (CK);
4. Technological Pedagogical knowledge (TPK);
5. Pedagogical Content knowledge (PCK);
6. Technological Content Knowledge (TCK); and
7. Technological Pedagogical and Content Knowledge (TPACK)

Scope and Delimitation

This study will be limited in describing the extent of Technological Pedagogical and Content Knowledge (TPACK) of secondary mathematics teachers of SMNHS.

This study is limited for the academic year of 2018 - 2019 which delimits the respondents to current secondary teachers of SMNHS both permanent and contractual.

Survey questionnaire will be used to gather the needed data of the study. Informal interviews and direct observation will also be conducted to random respondents to further understand and analyze the accumulated data gathered.

This study will be conducted on January - February 2019.

CHAPTER II

METHODS AND PROCEDURES

Research Design

This study utilized a quantitative research design aims to describe and synthesize the TPACK of secondary mathematics teachers of SMNHS.

Respondents/ Participants and Sampling Technique

This study will cover all teachers currently teaching Mathematics of SMNHS for the academic year 2018 - 2019, both contractual and permanent, major and non-majors. As such, the researcher will use total enumeration as a sampling technique.

Research Instruments

This research will use a questionnaire to gather the needed data from the study of Sahin (2011) entitled *Development of Survey of Technological, Pedagogical and Content Knowledge (TPACK)*.

Data Gathering Procedure

The questionnaire, upon approval of the school head, will be floated to all teachers of the institution. Enough time will be given to respondents to answer the survey to

ensure credibility of the results. After answering, the questionnaires will be collected immediately.

Confidentiality agreement was also discussed to reaffirm the participants that all answers will be kept confidential and omitted/destroyed if the participant chose to withdraw at the study for any given time.

Data Analysis

The data gathered will be tabulated, analyzed and interpreted using frequencies, percentages and weighted mean.

If missing data due to arbitrary or purposeful patterns of nonresponse will be discovered, list wise deletion will be used as a method, otherwise, if the missing data were found to be at random, it will be ignored for the purpose of giving its own question a merit of its context with the latter potentially not yielding a bias results.

Four (4) point rating scale will be used in interpreting the respondent's answer on the survey questionnaire as follows:

INTERVAL	DESCRIPTION	INTERPRETATION
3.26 - 4.00	Strongly agree	Very High Extent
2.51 - 3.25	Agree	High Extent
1.76 - 2.50	Slightly agree	Fair Extent
1.00 - 1.75	Disagree	Low Extent

CHAPTER III

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The following table presents the extent of Technological, Pedagogical and Content Knowledge (TPACK) of the secondary Mathematics teachers of Sta. Marcela National High School.

Table 1 presents the Technological Knowledge (TK) of Secondary Mathematics Teachers of SMNHS. It can be gleaned that using word - processor program such as MS word (3.57143, Very high extent) has been identified as the strongest knowledge of the teachers. This implies that teachers are well knowledgeable about word processors. This can be attributed to paper works that is needed to be done using such programs.

However, using picture editing programs such as Photoshop (2.28571, Fair extent) and manipulating specific area programs in the computers such as SPSS (2.42857, Fair extent) were identified as the weakest knowledge of the teachers. This means that teachers are not well oriented with certain applications in the computers design to enhance learning. This might be attributed to the very low impact

of such applications in teaching basic concepts in mathematics.

In summary it can be observed that the Technological Knowledge (TK) of the teachers is acceptable (3.02857, High extent) which means that teachers are well oriented on using technology in the teaching learning process.

Table 1: Technological Knowledge (TK) of Secondary Mathematics Teachers of SMNHS.

INDICATORS	Mean	Interpretation
Solving a technical problem with the computer	2.85714	High Extent
Understanding the basic computer hardware (ex., CD-Rom, mother-board, RAM) and their functions	3	High Extent
Understanding basic computer software (ex., Windows, Media Player) and their functions	3	High Extent
Using recent and trending computer technologies	2.57143	High Extent
Using a word-processor program (ex., MS Word)	3.57143	Very high Extent
Using an electronic spreadsheet program (ex., MS Excel)	3.28571	High Extent
Communicating through Internet tools (ex., Gmail, Messenger)	3.42857	High Extent
Using a picture editing program (ex., Paint, Photoshop)	2.28571	Fair Extent
Using a presentation program (ex., MS Powerpoint)	3.28571	High Extent
Saving data into a digital medium (ex., Flash Drive, CD, DVD, Memory Card)	3.28571	High Extent

Using area-specific software (ex. SPSS)	2.42857	Fair Extent
Using printers	3.14286	High Extent
Using projectors	3.28571	High Extent
Using scanners	3.14286	High Extent
Using digital camera	2.85714	High Extent
Total weighted mean	3.02857	High Extent

Table 2 presents the Pedagogical Knowledge (PK) of Secondary Mathematics Teachers of SMNHS. It can be gleaned that all indicators are of "high extent", managing class as the highest (3.28571, High extent). This implies that teachers are well knowledgeable about managing classes.

In summary it can be observed that the Pedagogical Knowledge (PK) of the teachers is acceptable (3.07143, High extent) which means that teachers are well oriented on using relevant methodologies and strategies when teaching mathematics concepts.

Table 2: Pedagogical Knowledge (PK) of Secondary Mathematics Teachers of SMNHS.

INDICATORS	Mean	Interpretation
Assessing student performance based on curriculum expectations	3.14286	High Extent
Eliminating individual differences among the students	3	High Extent

Using various evaluation methods and techniques in teaching Mathematics	3	High Extent
Applying different learning theories and approaches (ex, Constructivist Learning, Multiple Intelligence Theory, Project-based Learning)	3	High Extent
Addressing possible student learning difficulties and misconceptions	3	High Extent
Managing class	3.28571	High Extent
Total weighted mean	3.07143	High Extent

Table 3 presents the Content Knowledge (CK) of Secondary Mathematics Teachers of SMNHS. It can be gleaned that all indicators are of "high extent", developing class activities and projects that enhances student learning as the highest (3.42857, High extent). This implies that teachers are well verse on creating activities and related projects that is deemed to enhance and improve mathematics learning.

In summary it can be observed that the Content Knowledge (PK) of the teachers is acceptable (3.04762, High extent) which means that teachers are well knowledgeable on the content to be teach in mathematics.

Table 3: Content Knowledge (CK) of Secondary Mathematics Teachers of SMNHS.

INDICATORS	Mean	Interpretation
Understanding the key subjects/concepts in my area (Mathematics)	3.28571	High Extent
Developing class activities and projects that enhances student learning	3.42857	High Extent
Following recent developments and applications in my content area (Mathematics)	3.14286	High Extent
Recognizing leaders and innovators in my content area (Mathematics)	2.85714	High Extent
Following up-to-date resources (ex, books, journals) in my content area (Mathematics)	2.57143	High Extent
Following conferences, seminars, and activities in my content area (Mathematics)	3	High Extent
Total weighted mean	3.04762	High Extent

Table 4 presents the Technological Pedagogical Knowledge (TPK) of Secondary Mathematics Teachers of SMNHS. It can be gleaned that all indicators are of "high extent", choosing technologies appropriate for teaching/learning approaches and strategies as the highest (3.14286, High extent). This implies that teachers are well oriented with the technologies that is appropriate for an effective delivery of instruction.

In summary it can be observed that the Content Knowledge (PK) of the teachers is acceptable (2.89286, High extent) which means that teachers are well knowledgeable on identifying appropriate technology for a certain methodology or approach in teaching mathematics.

Table 4: Technological Pedagogical Knowledge (TPK) of Secondary Mathematics Teachers of SMNHS.

INDICATORS	Mean	Interpretation
Choosing technologies appropriate for my teaching/learning approaches and strategies	3.14286	High Extent
Using computer applications supporting student math learning (ex. Photomath)	2.85714	High Extent
Being able to select technologies useful for my teaching career	2.85714	High Extent
Evaluating appropriateness of a new technology (ex. smartphones, iPad) for enhancing teaching and learning in Mathematics	2.71429	High Extent
Total weighted mean	2.89286	High Extent

Table 5 presents the Pedagogical Content Knowledge (PCK) of Secondary Mathematics Teachers of SMNHS. It can be gleaned that all indicators are of "high extent", making connections among related concepts in the content are of Mathematics as the highest (3.42857, High extent). This implies that teachers are good at using strategies and

methodologies that will bridge the gap between and among the concepts to be discussed in mathematics.

In summary it can be observed that the Pedagogical Content Knowledge (PK) of the teachers is acceptable (3.14286, High extent) which means that teachers are well knowledgeable on using appropriate methodologies and strategies for a given concept in mathematics.

Table 5: Pedagogical Content Knowledge (PCK) of Secondary Mathematics Teachers of SMNHS.

INDICATORS	Mean	Interpretation
Selecting appropriate and effective teaching strategies for my content area (Mathematics)	3.14286	High Extent
Developing evaluation tests and surveys in my content area (Mathematics) (ex. Diagnostic test)	3	High Extent
Preparing a lesson plan including class/school-wide activities	3.28571	High Extent
Meeting objectives described in my lesson plan	3.28571	High Extent
Making connections among related concepts in my content area (Mathematics)	3.42857	High Extent
Making connections between my content area (Mathematics) and other related subjects	3	High Extent
Supporting concepts in my content area with outside (out-of-school) activities	2.85714	High Extent
Total weighted mean	3.14286	High Extent

Table 6 presents the Technological Content Knowledge (TCK) of Secondary Mathematics Teachers of SMNHS. It can be gleaned that all indicators are of "high extent except using area-specific computer applications (ex. Geogebra) (2.28571, Fair extent) and manipulating specific area programs in the computers such as SPSS (2.28571, Fair extent). This means that teachers are not well verse on using computer applications that could enrich their lessons.

In summary it can be observed that the Technological Content Knowledge (TCK) of the teachers is acceptable (2.92857, High extent) which means that teachers are well oriented on using technology appropriate for a given concept in mathematics.

Table 6: Technological Content Knowledge (TCK) of Secondary Mathematics Teachers of SMNHS.

INDICATORS	Mean	Interpretation
Using area-specific computer applications (ex. Geogebra)	2.28571	Fair Extent
Using various technologies in helping to reach course objectives easily in my lesson plan	3.14286	High Extent
Preparing a lesson plan requiring use of instructional technologies	3.14286	High Extent

Developing class activities and projects involving use of instructional technologies	3.14286	High Extent
Total weighted mean	2.92857	High Extent

Table 7 presents the Technological, Pedagogical and Content Knowledge (TPACK) of Secondary Mathematics Teachers of SMNHS. It can be gleaned that all indicators are of "high extent", which implies that the teachers are well knowledgeable on the three knowledge domains that will allow them to teach effectively. Further, this can be observe on the on the TPACK of the teachers (3.11429, High extent) which is quite acceptable based on standards.

Table 7: Technological, Pedagogical, and Content Knowledge (TPACK) of Secondary Mathematics Teachers of SMNHS.

INDICATORS	Mean	Interpretation
Integrating appropriate instructional methods and technologies into my content area (Mathematics)	3.14286	High Extent
Selecting contemporary strategies and technologies helping to teach my content effective	3.14286	High Extent
Teaching successfully by combining my content, pedagogy, and technology knowledge	3.28571	High Extent
Taking a leadership role among my colleagues in the integration of content, pedagogy, and technology in Mathematics.	2.85714	High Extent

Teaching a concept with various instructional strategies and computer applications	3.14286	High Extent
Total weighted mean	3.11429	High Extent

CHAPTER IV

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the aforementioned results, the extent of Technological, Pedagogical, and Content Knowledge (TPACK) of the secondary Mathematics teachers of Sta. Marcela National High School is "high" implying that they have sufficient knowledge to facilitate the 21st century classroom.

However, it is still recommended that the institution should not settle for it and continue develop programs and interventions that will improve the knowledge of teachers on the three key domains: Technological, Pedagogical and Content Knowledge which is deem important in delivering effective instruction.

It is also recommended that teachers should be oriented on the use and basic manipulation of related technologies since it is found that most of the teachers have basic knowledge on it.

REFERENCES

Archambault, L., & Crippen, K. (2009). Examining TPACK among K-12 online distance educators in the United States *Contemporary Issues in Technology and Teacher Education*, 9(1), 71-88.

Glaser. R. (1984). Education and thinking: The role of knowledge. *American Psychology*, 39(2), 93-104.

Harris, J. B. & Hofer, M. J. (2011). Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge in Action: A Descriptive Study of Secondary Teachers' Curriculum-Based, Technology-Related Instructional Planning. *Journal of Research on Technology in Education*, 43 (3). pp. 221 - 229

Koehler, M. J., & Mishra, P. (2009). What is technological pedagogical content knowledge? *Contemporary Issues in Technology and Teacher Education*, 9(1), 60-70.

Koehler, M.J., & Mishra, P. (2008). Introducing TPCK. AACTE Committee on Innovation and Technology (Ed.), *The handbook of technological pedagogical content knowledge (TPCK) for educators* (pp. 3-29). Mahwah, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.

Mishra, P., & Koehler, M. (2007). Technological pedagogical content knowledge (TPCK): Confronting the wicked problems of teaching with technology. In C. Crawford et al. (Eds.), *Proceedings of Society for Information Technology and Teacher Education International Conference 2007* (pp. 2214-2226). Chesapeake, VA: Association for the Advancement of Computing in Education.

Mishra, P., & Koehler, M.J. (2006). Technological pedagogical content knowledge: A framework for integrating technology in teacher knowledge. *Teachers College Record*, 108(6), 1017-1054.

Niess, M. L., Ronau, R. N., Shafer, K. G., Driskell, S. O., Harper S. R., Johnston, C., Browning, C., Özgün-Koca, S. A., & Kersaint, G. (2009). Mathematics teacher TPACK standards and development model. *Contemporary Issues in Technology and Teacher Education*, 9(1), 4-24.

Putnam, R.T., & Borko, H. (2000). What do new views of knowledge and thinking have to say about research on teacher learning? *Educational Researcher*, 29(1), 4-15.

Shulman, L. (1986). Those who understand: Knowledge growth in teaching. *Educational Researcher*, 15(2), 4-14.

Shulman, L. S. (1987). Knowledge and teaching: Foundations of the new reform. *Harvard Educational Review*, 57(1), 1-22.

Sahin, Ismail (2011). Development of survey of technological pedagogical and content knowledge (TPACK). *TOJET: The Turkish Online Journal of Educational Technology*, 10 (1), pp. 97 - 105.